

Discoveries made by the users of searching devices and the public in 2019 and the new Heritage Conservation Act

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INTRODUCTION

The article summarises recent contributions of users of searching devices and the public in Estonia. This overview follows geographical distribution and introduces new sites types and archaeological finds in chronological order. Most of the finds were obtained by using metal detectors and only a few discoveries were made by chance (Table 1: nos 9, 28, 142, 143).

In 2019, 617 permits were issued by the National Heritage Board for the licensed hobby searchers, that is 134 permits more than last year (Rammo & Smirnova 2019). The number of licensed searches has rapidly increased, but not all of the hobby searchers found and reported archaeological finds. At the same time, the volume of archaeological finds that was handed over by the detectorists has grown significantly in comparison to previous years – the table includes 111 records (47%) more than the table that lists finds from the 2018 (Rammo & Smirnova 2019, table 1). This can be, at least partly, explained by the implementation of the new Heritage Conservation Act, which took effect in May 2019. The new regulation specifies the use of search devices and it is discussed at the end of the paper (see also Kadakas, this volume).

SOME REMARKS ON DATA

As in previous years (e.g. Rammo & Kangert 2018), the information about new discoveries is summarised in Table 1 that forms the basis of this overview. Some deliberate exclusions have been made for better understanding and clarity of the information. For instance, finds that cannot be identified or their dating remains uncertain at the current state of the research were left out. Also single finds or assemblages that originate from the 19th–20th centuries (e.g. modern coins, buttons, tobacco pipe details) were excluded from the dataset, but the exception was made for unique or rare stray finds. A site is listed in the table if the artefacts

Fig. 1. Finds and sites discovered by users of searching devices or by the public in 2019. Administrative and settlement units, Estonian Land Board 01.10.2020

Jn 1. 2019. aastal otsinguvahendiga ja juhuslikult avastatud muistised ja leiud. Haldusjaotus: Maa-amet 01.10.2020
Map / Kaart: Andres Kimber

and the information of the find spot have reached the National Heritage Board in 2019 regardless of the time of the actual discovery. Lastly, it should be noted that many find spots overlap with already known antiquities and the number of new sites is somewhat smaller than presented in Table 1. For instance, 17 sites from Harju County have been mentioned in the previous papers that introduce new finds (Rammo *et al.* 2015, 2016, 2017; Rammo & Kangert 2018; Rammo & Smirnova 2019). Despite this, the number of reported sites has never been so high and the amount of objects handed over to the MA has tremendously increased, which challenges the existing system (see below).

RESULTS

Northern parts of Estonia (Harju, Ida-Viru, Järva, Lääne-Viru, and Rapla Counties)

Most of the finding places reported by the licensed hobby searchers are situated in the northern parts of Estonia and especially in Harju County, but also the number of reported sites and finds from Järva County exceeds earlier years (Table 1). Several sites from Ida-Viru County continued to be under close attention of hobby searchers (e.g. nos 55, 78–81, 84) and the same can be said about Järvamaa (e.g. nos 99, 104–105, 116–117) and Rapla Counties (e.g. nos 146, 147).

Although the number of sites is quite high, only some of them could be associated with a certain archaeological context such as burial ground (e.g. nos 2, 39, 40, 99, 124, 134, 147), a settlement site (e.g. nos 16, 24, 39, 113, 132, 147) or a hoard (e.g. no 82). As mentioned above, several sites were already known and finds reported from these in 2019 have a similar nature

to those reported earlier. For instance, single coins found from the same spot as a coin hoard with similar date are probably connected and can be interpreted as a part of this hoard (e.g. nos 68, 105). Finds from some formerly known sites of other types (e.g. nos 33, 99, 146, 147) do not change previous interpretation either.

Still, the majority of finds are treated as stray finds, but this may change in the future when more information becomes available. Unfortunately, the high number of artefacts and sites discovered in the recent years limits the capacity of conducting further studies on spot and just a few sites have been examined by archaeologists (e.g. no 124).

The oldest artefacts from northern Estonia are a socketed axe from Puhkova (no 70) and another from Soldina (no 74) dating from the Late Bronze Age (1100–500 BC). According to Kristiina Paavel (2019) the Puhkova find (Fig. 2) belongs to the Akozino-Mälär type of socketed axes and this is only the fourth specimen found in Estonia. Early Iron Age (500 BC–450 AD) artefacts are also scarce, but the amount of such finds has grown yearly. A rare Pre-Roman (500 BC–50 AD) tenon axe with a loop for the handle was found in Jõeküla (no 101). Finds of Roman Iron Age date (50–450 AD) are more numerous: several fragments of jewellery such as bow fibulae (nos 1, 11, 58), an enamelled penannular brooch (no 127), a bracelet (no 11), and a finger-ring have been discovered (no 67). Active usage of metal detectors has steadily increased the number of Roman coins known from Estonia (Koovit & Kiudsoo 2016, 71–72; Rammo *et al.* 2017, 198) and 2019 brought an addition to the existing finds (no 32; Kiudsoo 2019a). Also, a grinding stone from Kantküla (no 9) that was found without using a searching device, has probably a Bronze Age or Early Iron Age date, but a somewhat later date cannot be ruled out (Tamla 2019).

Eight iron socketed axes from five sites (nos 62, 72, 73, 83, 85) and a spearhead (no 26) that are dated to the Early Iron Age until the Middle Iron Age can be pointed out as well. All the socketed axes were discovered in the vicinity of Kohtla-Järve. In addition, some ornaments and their fragments from the second half of the Middle Iron Age were found (e.g. nos 61, 130). Another remarkable find comes from Koila (no 12) and it consists of two ring-headed dress pins with a 7th–9th century date.

The bulk of the material belongs to the Late Iron Age (800–1200/1250 AD) until the Middle Ages or the Modern Period. Viking Age (800–1050 AD) finds are often coins and pieces of ornaments. For example, a burial ground from Allikjärve (no 99) contained burnt fragments of jewellery such as cast bracelets with thickening terminals (Kuriso 2020a) that are characteristic for the first half of the Late Iron Age (Tvauri 2012, 162). But all together, pieces of jewellery with a firm Viking Age date are not very numerous and in this light two brooches deserve to be pointed out.

The first of those two is a box brooch of Gotlandic origin (Fig. 3), which women used to fasten outer garments (Thedéen 2012, 61). Varja specimen represents the earliest type of box brooches and is dated to the 9th century (Kiudsoo 2019b). The total number of such brooches found from Gotland exceeds 800 pieces (Thunmark-Nylén 2006, 64), but only around 30 finds have been discovered outside Gotland (Thedéen 2012, 66). The second example is a

Fig. 2. Socketed axe from Puhkova (no 70).

Jn 2. Puhkova putkkirves (nr 70).

(AI 8285.)

Photo / Foto: Kristiina Paavel

Fig. 3. Box brooch from Varja (no 81).

Jn 3. *Varja karpsõlg* (no 81).
(AI 8126.)

Photo / Foto: Mauri Kiudsoo

large crossbow-shaped brooch from the early 9th century that was found in Ebavere (no 124). The brooch is decorated in Nordic animal style. Such well-preserved items are not very common in Estonia, but an analogous brooch was recently found in Haljala (Mägi 2018, front cover; more analogous finds in Mägi, this volume). Large crossbow-shaped brooches were worn primarily by men in some regions of the present day Latvia (Tvauri 2012, 134). Burnt items in the Ebavere find spot indicate that there was a burial ground with cremations.

Final Iron Age (1050–1200/1250) finds represent a wide variety of artefacts of which ornaments and dress accessories are the most common type of objects. In general, most of the finds are typical to the period, containing bracelets, brooches, pendants, pieces of chain arrangements, belt fittings, mounts, etc. Among more notable pieces are a flower style chain holder from Kaasiku (no 7), an axe-shaped pendant from Nurmetu (no 128), and a flail-ball from Aidu (no 56). Chain holders with a central palmette motif were spread in the areas of the Livs in northern Latvia, where they appeared in the late 12th century and were most intensively used during the 13th century (Spirģis 2008, 479); such finds are atypical in Estonia. The Nurmetu axe-pendant belongs to the Makarov's type 2 axe-shaped pendants that are modelled after broad battle axes and its Russian counterparts are dated to the 11th–12th centuries (Makarov 1992). It is a finely executed specimen and probably one of the first of its kind found in Estonia (Kurisoo 2020b). A unique find in Estonian context is also a flail-ball, which may be dated to the 12th or the beginning of the 13th century (pers. comm. Ain Mäesalu, TÜ).

Artefacts from the Middle Ages (1200/1250–1558 AD) and from the Modern Period (1558 AD onwards) are mostly ornaments and dress accessories common with the rural population (e.g. brooches, finger-rings, rumbler bells, pendants, mounts). The various buttons, pewter bullets, coins, and thimbles became especially numerous in the Modern Period. Two find assemblages, however, include fragments of the 17th–18th century peasant women's waist ornaments (nos 41, 69), which fragments have been unearthed more often in recent years (Rammo & Smirnova 2019, 270). Exceptional is a gilt silver finger-ring from Kumna (no 17), which might be related to the nearby manor (Russow 2020a). Another noteworthy discovery is a remarkably well preserved Early Modern Period pewter jug found in the field (no 58) as pewter items decompose easily while deposited in the soil. In general, these results correspond with the trends observed in the previous years (e.g. Rammo & Kangert 2018; Rammo & Smirnova 2019).

Western parts of Estonia (Lääne, Pärnu, and Saare Counties)

Notably less information is available on the finds recovered from the western parts of Estonia (Fig. 1). The main reason for this is thought to be poor reporting of artefacts and find spots (Rammo *et al.* 2017, 198). For instance, only five sites from Lääne and two from Pärnu County are listed, while both items from Pärnu County were found accidentally. The first of these, a stone adze from Eense (no 142), has not yet been separately studied, but the shape of it suggests a Stone Age date (pers. comm. Kristiina Johanson, TÜ). The second example is a

medieval antler axe that was found from the Pärnu beach (no 143; Reppo 2020). Such finds are rare in Estonia and less than ten specimens are known (Luik & Haak 2017). The Pärnu specimen has no decoration and it seems that the axe is unfinished (Fig. 4). The function of such items is debatable: some of them may have been used as hammers, but richly decorated objects could also have carried a symbolic meaning that was linked with their axe-shaped appearance (Luik & Haak 2017).

Nevertheless, a positive trend can be observed in the last few years with finds discovered from the island of Saaremaa, where the number of reported finds has rapidly grown. 44 find places from Saaremaa have been listed in the table, some of them were discovered years ago (e.g. in 2015), but the information reached the MA in 2019. Several find spots include micro-regions that have been searched repeatedly for years by different persons. For instance, the border area of Varpe, Leedri and Lümanda villages, where numerous artefacts from the Late Iron Age until the Modern Period have been collected over a long period (nos 167, 173, 174, 186–188). This results in many small sets of finds that are treated together in this overview. Challenges related to such find assemblages and search activities have been discussed earlier (Rammo & Kangert 2018, 214).

Although stray finds dominate, there are several find spots in western parts of Estonia that can be interpreted as burial grounds and most of these sites have Late Iron Age dates (e.g. nos 151, 160, 187, 189). Also, one Viking Age hoard was discovered from Varpe (no 188) and another find (no 191) that was discovered several years ago can be associated with the Viidumäe sacrificial place that is now a protected monument (MA reg. no 30391; Mägi *et al.* 2015; 2016). There is little information about clearly identified settlement sites (no 187) and fieldwork is needed for clarifying the nature of many of the find spots. In addition, a harbour site at Mullutu (no 178) deserves noting. According to Marika Mägi (2019), the finds correspond to the material found from known harbour sites in Saaremaa and more generally from northern Europe, and the artefacts suggest that Mullutu harbour was used from the 8th to 15th centuries.

Artefacts from the first half of the prehistory are few in number and Late Iron Age objects clearly dominate among the finds that were handed over to the MA. The oldest artefacts were found at Meedla (no 177) and they include a Bronze Age copper alloy axe and an iron axe with a broad date ranging from the Roman Iron Age to the Migration Period. More noteworthy pieces from the Late Iron Age include several items unique in Estonian context, for example a Gotlandic box brooch from Mullutu (no 178) and an animal head-shaped brooch from Lümanda (no 174). As the box brooches are rare outside Gotland, the finds from Mullutu and Varja (see above) are exceptional also in the wider context of Baltic Sea region. The animal head-shaped brooch is probably the first of such ornaments that reached the archaeological collections in Estonia. Similar animal head-shaped brooches have been found in Gotland and they are dated to the Viking Age (e.g. Thunmark-Nylén 1995, fig. 454: 1, 455: 3). A unique Ringerike style gilt sword pommel is significant, but regrettably, it is only known that the object was found somewhere in the historic Kihelkonna parish (Jets 2019), and thus, it is not

Fig. 4. Antler axe from Pärnu (no 143).

Jn 4. Pärnust leitud sarvest kirves (nr 143).
(PäMu.)

Photo / Foto: Heidi Luik

included in the table. Finds from the Middle Ages and the Modern Period are also common, but only four sites include find assemblages that do not contain items from the previous periods. The most notable finds are three cast iron ingots from Kehila (no 157) that may originate from a smithy site (Saage 2019a).

Southern parts of Estonia (Tartu, Jõgeva, Viljandi, Põlva, Valga, and Võru Counties)

Data about the southern parts of Estonia is relatively scarce and only a few sites are listed from Viljandi (7), Põlva (5), Valga (7) and Võru (2) Counties. Unfortunately, it is a continuous trend that has not changed over the time (Rammo & Kangert 2018, 214). But on the positive side, Tartu County stands out with 29 listed sites. Information about Jõgeva County has remained similar to the last few years. In Viljandi County, a traditional joint fieldwork of hobby searchers, MA, and archaeologists in order to locate the St Matthew's Day battlefield took place also in 2019 (nos 229, 230; see Konsa *et al.* 2019 for earlier events).

The increased number of find spots from Tartu County are connected to the intensified search activity at the Peipsi Lowland (Fig. 1). The artefacts range from fishing equipment to details of dress and ornaments and the majority of the datable finds (e.g. Orthodox crosses, signet rings, coins) originate from the Modern Period starting from the 16th century. Most of the finds from the Peipsi Lowland are difficult to contextualise, as they were collected from the shallow coastal water of the lake, and thus, they are regarded as stray finds (nos 137–139, 141, 196, 203, 204, 212, 216, 218). It is likely that many of these items originate from the occupation layers and burial grounds once situated on the shore, but now washed in the lake. For example, Praaga (no 204) used to be an island at the mouth of the River Emajõgi and this knowledge helps to contextualise some of the findings. Various types of round shots, spearheads and lances along with numerous dirk-knives and knife handles suggest that a possible outpost was located at Praaga during the times of conflict in the 16th and 17th centuries (Saage 2019b; Saage & Tvaauri 2019).

Other site types from the southern parts of Estonia include burial grounds (e.g. nos 93, 94, 199, 200, 210, 214, 228, 232), hoards (nos 208, 222, 226, 234) and settlement sites (nos 94, 98, 193, 194, 204, 207, 209, 215, 222–225, 227, 230). Dwelling sites were used over a longer period and artefacts usually suggest a broad dating between the Late Iron Age and the Modern

Period. Finds that can be associated with burial places, however, have either the Late Iron Age date or the artefacts refer to the Middle Ages or the Modern Period (see below).

This year four hoards were discovered with metal detectors. One assemblage belongs to the Viking Age and consists of coins (no 234; Konsa *et al.*, this volume). The other hoards, which contain mostly coins and ornaments dating from the 16th–17th centuries, were likely deposited during the events of the Livonian War (1558–1583), the famine years in 1601–1603 or the Swedish-Polish wars (1600–1629). The hoard from Raigaste (no 208) contains various beads (Fig. 5; e.g. silver, amber, chalcedony, pewter, glass) that

Fig. 5. Remains of a pewter jug and some beads from the Raigaste hoard (no 208).

Jn 5. Kannu jäänused ja mõned helmed Raigaste aardest (nr 208).

(TÜ 2889.)

Photo / Foto: Riina Rammo

were hidden inside a pewter jug (Tvauri 2020). 22 round and rectangular sheet pendants, nine fragments of spiral tubes and a piece of yarn compose the Soontaga hoard (no 226). It is likely that sheet pendants form one jewellery set that was made in the 15th or 16th century (Tvauri 2019). Lastly, fragments of a neck ornament made of coins and chains from Killinge (no 222) composed probably a hoard that was dispersed by ploughing (Rammo 2020). Killinge coins were minted in the 16th century (Rammo 2020) and similar ornaments were used in the 16th and 17th centuries (Kiudsoo 2008; Tvauri 2014).

As in the rest of Estonia, artefacts from the first half of the prehistory are seldom found and a Bronze Age axe fragment from Sürgavere (no 235) can be named as an example. Only two dress pin fragments in larger find sets could originate from the Middle Iron Age, more precisely from the Migration Period (nos 91, 200).

As expected, Late Iron Age objects dominate among prehistoric finds and the majority belong to the widespread types of objects. Though a few exceptional ornaments with Late Iron Age date such as a Karelian origin (?) comb-shaped pendant and an atypical closed bracelet from the 11th century were found from the coastal area of Lake Peipsi (nos 194, 218). Altogether three Late Iron Age sword scabbard chapes have been collected (nos 196, 219, 236), which are exceptional finds in Estonia. For example, Tomsons's IIIb type sword scabbard chape (Tomsons 2018, 149–151) was found in Kasepää hamlet (Fig. 6; Juurik 2019) and another with a face decoration in Pindi (no 236). In several cases the Late Iron Age artefacts are associated with burial grounds. Fragments of copper alloy jewellery and dress accessories, sometimes clearly burnt and fragmented, dominate in such find assemblages (e.g. nos 93, 94, 200, 206, 211).

Several find assemblages with a broad date (e.g. no 206) include often smaller find sets that have medieval or post-medieval date and that are typical to the village cemeteries (e.g. Valk 2001). The latter include various brooches, finger-rings, bells, coins, and belt fittings. A rare find is a spout of a lavabo from the 15th–16th centuries that was found in Alavere near Laiuse church (no 87). It has zoomorphic decoration and similar vessels were used for washing hands (Russow 2020b). Interestingly, three more fragments of peculiar knife-shaped ornaments (Luik 2019a–b), similar to items delivered to the MA in 2017 (Rammo & Kangert 2018, 213, fig. 7), were discovered; two of them on the island of Piirissaare (nos 212, 216) and one in Lapetukme (no 200). Such items are assumed to be of eastern Finno-Ugric origin and of medieval date (Luik 2018), but their function has remained unclear.

Fig. 6. Sword scabbard chape from Lake Peipsi near Kasepää (no 196).

Jn 6. Mõõgatupeots Kasepää lähedalt Peipsi järvest (nr 196).

(TÜ 2850.)

Photo / Foto: Riina Rammo

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEW HERITAGE CONSERVATION ACT

The Heritage Conservation Act has regulated the use of metal detectors in Estonia since 2011. All hobby searchers need a licence that can be applied after passing a specific training on archaeological finds and monuments. The licence system has given the law-abiding detectorists an opportunity to practice their hobby legally and provide new information about archaeological sites that were unknown to the archaeological community. However, the fact that licence was only needed when searching for objects with cultural value, provided a loophole for conducting illegal searches.

The new regulation version that became effective on the 1st of May 2019 brought changes to the search device regulation (e.g. Kadakas 2019; Smirnova 2019). Now the licence is needed when using metal detector, magnet, or sonar outside of a densely populated area (town or village), regardless of the intention. Other notable changes include the notification system, a shorter deadline for reports and longer validity of the licences (five years). All hobby searchers are obliged to notify the MA about where and when they are planning to use the search device in advance. This can be done via the National Registry of Cultural Monuments, email or SMS. The deadline for the report is one month after the search activity.

The strength of this new system lies in the opportunity to separate the law-abiding hobby searchers from looters. Now, the National Heritage Board is able to check in real time if persons conducting a search have submitted a notification about their search and have a licence, or the activity should be investigated at once. Also, the system of ongoing reporting has clear benefits for everyone involved. The detectorists report after each search, which helps to ensure that the information about finds and find spots is more accurate when compared to the old system where one comprehensive report was submitted at the end of the year. Hopefully, the National Heritage Board is able to give quicker feedback to licence owners and new finds reach conservators and researchers faster.

However, the rising number of people with licenses, but also the amount of reports and finds turned over to the state, have flooded the MA with information. For instance, about 2500 reports and notifications were sent to the MA between the 1st of May and the 31st of December in 2019. Moreover, in 2019 195 acts for handing over finds were signed that contain information about over 435 find spots. The new system needs time to settle, but these numbers demonstrate that the interest in archaeology is growing as more people attend training, apply for licence and report their search activities and finds.

SUMMARISING REMARKS

The geographical distribution of the reported find spots is similar to the previous years, but notably more information was gained about Saare and Tartu Counties. Finds from the first half of the prehistory are scarce and the majority of the reported finds fall into the period from the end of the prehistory to the end of the modern era. The implementation of the new Heritage Conservation Act has promoted reporting activities, which helps to improve the protection of archaeological monuments and advances cooperation between the hobby searchers and the archaeological community in Estonia.

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Table 1. Finds discovered by users of searching devices and stray finds reported to the National Heritage Board in 2019. Former parish name (if different from the present municipality name) is given in brackets.

Table 1. Otsinguvahendiga leitud ja juhuslikult avastatud leiud, mis jõudsid 2019. aastal Muinsuskaitseametisse. Sulgudes on esitatud kihelkond, juhul kui see erineb kehtivast haldusjaotusest.
Compiled by / Koostanud: Maria Smirnova, Riina Rammo & Tuuli Kurisoo

C – cemetery, burial place / kalmistu, matmispaik

F – stray find / juhuleid

H – hoard, deposit find / peitleid

S – settlement site / asulakoht

SP – sacrificial place / ohverdamiskoht

HS – harbour site / sadamakoht

M – manufacturing site / tootmisega seotud muistis

No / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Admin. unit / Haldusüksus	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
HARJUMAA								
1	Aavere	F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Crossbow fibulae, cannon ball	Roman Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Tammet
2	Adra	C, F	Harku (Keila)	Coin pendants, rectangular ornament link, belt fittings (e.g. mounts), penannular brooch, chain fragments, ringlets, finger-ring, burnt copper alloy items	Late Iron Age, Early Modern Period	AI 8142	A. Haruk	K. Tasuja
3	Alliku	F	Saue (Keila)	Fragments of dress pin	Late Iron Age	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
4	Arava	F	Anija (Kose)	Icon	18th–19th c	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Reppo
5	Ihasalu	F	Jõelähtme	Silver coin	9th c	AI 8132	Anonymous	M. Kiudsoo
6	Järsi	F	Raasiku (Jüri)	Mount fragments, inkwell	Late Iron Age, 18th c	AI 8199	E. Heinsalu	E. Russow, M. Reppo
7	Kaasiku	F	Saue (Nissi)	Openwork chain holder	Late Iron Age	MA	A. Ksentsov	M. Reppo
8	Kadaka	F	Rae (Jüri)	Fragment of chain holder, copper alloy item	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8110	Anonymous	K. Tasuja
9	Kantküla	F	Kose	Grinding stone	Late Bronze Age – Iron Age	AI 8143	A. Kivistik	Ü. Tamla
10	Kata	C?, F	Kose	Coins, pendants	Late Iron Age, Early Modern Period	AI 8138	V. Volkov	K. Tasuja
11	Kautjala	C?	Rae (Jüri)	Fragments of crossbow fibulae, bracelet	3rd–4th c	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
12	Koila	F	Jõelähtme	2 ring-headed dress pins	7th–9th c	AI 8210	A. Karindi	R. Rammo
13	Kolga	F	Kuusalu	Lunula pendant	Late Iron Age	MA	V. Tkatchuk	G.-K. Lutter
14	Kopli	F	Rae (Jüri)	Cruciform pendant, rectangular ornament link	Late Iron Age	AI 8109	Anonymous	K. Tasuja
15	Kotka	F	Kuusalu	Penannular brooch, button	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	V. Tkatchuk	G.-K. Lutter

No / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Admin. unit / Haldusüksus	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
16	Kumna	S?	Harku (Keila)	Penannular brooch, chain holder, fragment of comb-shaped pendant, trapezoid pendant, spearhead?, bracelet fragment, belt fittings of metal, needle case?, scale weight	Late Iron Age – Early Modern Period	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
17	Kumna	F	Harku (Keila)	Gilt silver finger-ring	Early Modern Period – Modern Period	MA	A. Sudovykh	E. Russov
18	Kuusemäe	F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Coin pendants, coin	Late Iron Age Middle Ages	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Reppo
19	Kütke	F	Harku (Keila)	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age	AI 8129	V. Volkov	Ü. Tamla
20	Kütke	F	Harku (Keila)	Strap end	Middle Ages?	AI 8140	V. Volkov	H. Luik
21	Lilli	S?, F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Coins, dress pin fragment, rectangular ornament link, pewter finger-ring, copper alloy clasp	Viking Age – Modern Period	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Tammet, M. Reppo
22	Loo	F	Jõelähtme	Bracelet	Late Iron Age	AI 8156	D. Tihonov	T. Kurisoo
23	Maardu	F	Jõelähtme	Chain separator, buckle, fragment of metal item	12th–13th c	MA	Anonymous	
24	Nurme	S, F	Saue (Nissi)	Fragments of various finger-rings, trapezoid pendant, coin pendant, handle of spoon	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA, AI 8160	T. Toomsalu	T. Kurisoo
25	Nurme	S	Saue (Nissi)	Silver coin fragment, mounts	8th c, Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA, AI 8159	T. Toomsalu	M. Kiudsoo
26	Oru	F	Kose	Spearhead, knife handle fragment	Roman Iron Age – Migration Period, Modern Period	AI 8157	D. Podjakov	T. Kurisoo
27	Paasiku	C?, F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Mount, metal vessel fragment, pewter bullet	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Tammet
28	Pae	F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Finger-ring	Modern Period	MA	H. Jarvis	
29	Palvere	C?	Kose	Penannular brooch, cruciform and trapezoid pendant, bracelet fragments	Late Iron Age	AI 8227, AI 8230	A. Pluss	H. Luik
30	Palvere	C?	Kose	Penannular brooch fragment, trapezoid pendant	Late Iron Age	AI 8228	A. Pluss	H. Luik
31	Paunküla	F?	Kose	Chain holder fragment, pendant fragment, belt fittings (buckle, mount), tweezers, metal objects	Late Iron Age	AI 8231	A. Pluss	H. Luik
32	Rae	F	Rae (Jüri)	Roman coin	2nd c	AI 8128	V. Volkov	M. Kiudsoo
33	Rahula	C, S, F	Saku (Keila)	Chain holder, bells, small round brooch, finger-ring fragment, belt fittings, button, metal tripod fragment, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA, AI 8108	J. Terehov, Anonymous	K. Tasuja
34	Raveliku	F	Kose	Pendant	Middle Iron Age?	AI 8229	A. Pluss	H. Luik
35	Raveliku	C?	Kose	Burnt copper alloy items	Late Iron Age	MA	A. Agurauja	
36	Ruu	H?	Jõelähtme	2 silver coins	End of 16th c	AI 8145	V. Tkatchuk	M. Kiudsoo

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37	Rõõsa	F	Kose	Buckle, copper alloy rings	11th c	AI 8137	A. Pluss	K. Tasuja
38	Saha	F	Jõelähtme	Brooch fragment, chain holder	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	AI 8111	J. Gaidai	K. Tasuja
39	Saue	C, S	Saku (Keila)	Pendants, finger-rings, mounts, pewter plaques, bells, belt fittings, burnt metal items, button, lock, spoon fragment	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
40	Saula	C	Kose	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (penannular brooch, finger-ring), belt fittings of metal (mounts)	Late Iron Age	AI 8196	D. Podjakov	M. Reppo
41	Saunja	H?, F	Kuusalu	Silver beads, brooch fragment, copper alloy waist ornament (chain holders, chains, ringlets)	Late Middle Ages – Modern Period	AI 8091	K. Kasemets	M.-L. Posti
42	Sookaera-Metsanurga	F	Saku (Jüri)	Spearhead	Late Iron Age	AI 8131	J. Ojabstein	M. Kiudsoo
43	Suurküla	F	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Trapezoid pendant, scale weight, mount	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8239	M. Meipalu	H. Luik
44	Tammiku	F	Kose	Brooch	Early Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
45	Tutermaa	S?	Harku (Keila)	Fragments of pendants, bell	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
46	Tuulevälja	F	Rae (Jüri)	Finger-ring, belt strap	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8107	J. Gaidai	K. Tasuja
47	Tõhelgi	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Horse-shaped pendant, cruciform pendant, spur fragment	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Tammets
48	Uuearu	F	Anija (Kose)	Penannular brooches, finger-rings	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	O. Sidorov	M. Reppo
49	Vaidasoo	F	Rae (Jüri)	Coin, trapezoid pendant, harness pendant?, rings, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	T. Niklus	
50	Valingu	F	Saue (Keila)	S-shaped pendant, finger-ring, chain holder	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
51	Viskla	F	Kose	Pewter pendant	16th–18th c	AI 8136	A. Aguraiuja	K. Tasuja
52	Viskla	F	Kose	Fragments of burnt copper alloy items, penannular brooch, signet ring, thimble	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	A. Aguraiuja	
53	Voose	F	Anija (Kose)	Pendants, bells, bracelet fragments, finger-ring, coin fragments, buckle	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8232	A. Pluss	H. Luik
54	Üksnurme	F	Saku (Keila)	Fragment of bird-shaped pendant	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
IDA-VIRUMAA								
55	Aa	F	Lüganuse	Coin, pewter cruciform pendant, strap end, spearhead, knife handle fragment, lock, slag	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	E. Alkinas, E. Kessel	M. Reppo
56	Aidu	F	Lüganuse	Flail ball, penannular brooch, dress pin	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA, AI 8165	K. Kartau, H. Jõesaar	T. Kurisoo
57	Aidu-Liiva	F	Lüganuse	Bracelet fragment	11th c	MA	E. Alkinas	M. Reppo

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58	Amula	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Cross-ribbed fibula, coins, pewter jug, knife, hobnail, metal items	Roman Iron Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period	AI 8124	E. Kessel, M. Stadnik	
59	Arumäe	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Pendant fragment	Late Iron Age	MA	Y. Chernyshov	
60	Auvere	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Bells	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	MA	V. Maksimov	M. Reppo
61	Auvere	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Bow fibulae fragments, penannular brooch, lunula pendant, mounts, jewellery fragments	Middle Iron Age – Early Modern Period	MA	P. Stimmer	
62	Edise	F	Lüganuse (Jõhvi)	Iron socketed axes, pewter pendant, ornamented metal item, candle holder	Roman Iron Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	E. Alkinas, E. Kessel	M. Reppo
63	Edivere	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Silver sheet pendant, finger-ring	Middle Ages	MA	P. Malm	R. Rammo
64	Illuka	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Coins, cruciform pendants, chain separator	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	P. Malm	R. Rammo
65	Kukruse	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Silver sheet pendant, metal item fragments	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	E. Kessel	
66	Laagna	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Fragments of silver coin	10th c	AI 8226	R. Romanov	H. Luik
67	Matka	F	Lüganuse	Coin, bracelets, finger-ring, key, mount, axe, lance head, hobnail	Roman Iron Age, Viking Age – Modern Period	MA	E. Kessel	
68	Moldova	H	Lüganuse	Silver coins	11th c	MA	A. Smirnov	I. Leimus
69	Ohakvere	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Metal beads, cruciform pendant, copper alloy waist ornament fragments	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	P. Malm	R. Rammo
70	Puhkova	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Socketed axe, signet ring	Late Bronze Age, Early Modern Period	AI 8285	R. Beyu	K. Paavel
71	Pühajõe	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Sieve-shaped pendant, coins	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	S. Zaitsev	M. Kiudsoo
72	Saka	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Coins, gilt silver sheet ornament, small round brooch, penannular brooches, pewter beads, finger-ring, mounts, needle case, spearhead, arrowhead, bolts, knives, strike-a-lights, parts of horse harness, spurs, sickle, hobnails, iron socketed axes, axe, metal items	Pre-Roman Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	E. Kessel	
73	Saka	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Iron socketed axe	Early Iron Age – Middle Iron Age	AI 8127	E. Kessel	H. Luik
74	Soldina	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Socketed axe	Late Bronze Age	MA	D. Šutov	K. Paavel

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75	Soldina	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Coins	Viking Age, Early Modern Period – Modern Period	MA	D. Šutov	
76	Sompa	H?, F	Jõhvi	Silver coins	10th–11th c	MA	A. Smirnov	I. Leimus
77	Sompa	F	Jõhvi	Fragment of heart-shaped pendant	Early Modern Period	MA	V. Maksimov	M. Reppo
78	Varja	H?	Lüganuse	Coins	Middle Ages	MA	R. Vinkler	
79	Varja	H?, F	Lüganuse	Coins	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	R. Vinkler	
80	Varja	H?, F	Lüganuse	Bracelets, pewter pendants and beads, copper alloy bead, finger-rings, bell, belt fittings, fragments of scales, key, pewter ingot, metal object	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA, AI 8126	A. Šovkunenko, E. Kessel, I. Letitski	M. Reppo, M. Kiudsoo
81	Varja	F	Lüganuse	Box brooch, metal bowl	Viking Age, Middle Ages?	AI 8126	E. Kessel	M. Kiudsoo
82	Vitsiku	H	Lüganuse (Jõhvi)	Silver coin, silver ingots, mount	Viking Age	MA	E. Kessel	
83	Vitsiku	F	Lüganuse (Jõhvi)	Iron socketed axe	Roman Iron Age – Middle Iron Age	MA	E. Kessel	
84	Voorepera	F	Lüganuse	Comb-shaped pendant fragment	12th–13th c	MA	E. Alkinas	M. Reppo
85	Voorepera	F	Lüganuse	Iron socketed axe, penannular brooch, bracelet fragments	Early Iron Age, Late Iron Age	MA	E. Kessel	

JÕGEVAMAA

86	Alavere	H?, S	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Coin fragments, neck-ring fragments, dress pin, horse-shaped pendant, cruciform pendant, pewter pendants, bracelets, finger-ring, bells, buttons	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	J. Naaber, K. Keske	M. Kiudsoo, M. Reppo
87	Alavere	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Spout of metal vessel	15th–16th c	TÜ 2914	J. Naaber	E. Russow
88	Järvepera	F	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Small round brooch, bell, metal items	Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
89	Kaude	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Pendant fragments, bracelet fragment, mounts	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	K. Keske	
90	Mustvee	F	Mustvee (Torma)	Iron axe	Middle Ages	MA	A. Vasjagin	
91	Patjala	C?, F	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Dress pin fragment, penannular brooches, finger-rings, pendants, bells, mounts	7th–8th c – Modern Period	MA	S. Vinokurov	M.-L. Posti
92	Tapiku	F	Põltsamaa	Signet rings, bells, belt fittings and horse harness of metal, spur, bullet	Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ	S. Vinokurov	M.-L. Posti
93	Tõikvere	C	Jõgeva (Torma)	Burnt bracelet and chain fragments, melted metal items	Late Iron Age	TÜ 2891	E. Pärtelpoeg	R. Juurik

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94	Tõivere	C, S	Põltsamaa	Penannular brooches, dress pin head, finger-rings, bells, bracelet, coin pendants, mounts, button, thimble, bullet	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2900	S. Vinokurov, K. Keske	M.-L. Posti
95	Varbevere	F	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Penannular brooches, round brooch, bells, dress pin fragment, finger-rings, mounts, buttons	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ	S. Vinokurov	M.-L. Posti
96	Võduvere	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Penannular brooches, small round brooch, signet ring, bell, pendant, comb, knife handle fragment	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	S. Vinokurov	M.-L. Posti
97	Vägeva	F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Penannular brooch, brooch needle, button, bullets, hobnail, chisels	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	P. Laidre	R. Saage
98	Änkküla	S	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Coins, finger-rings, cruciform pendant, bell, mount	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	J. Naaber	R. Juurik

JÄRVAMAA

99	Allikjärve	C, F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Burnt copper alloy jewellery (penannular brooches, bracelets, chains, chain holders) and belt fittings, scale weights, thimble fragment, horse-shaped toy, buttons	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	AI 8163	A. Vares	T. Kurisoo
100	Ageri	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Pendant, mount	Late Iron Age	AI 8135	D. Podjakov	K. Tasuja
101	Jõeküla	F	Järva (Koeru)	Tenon axe	Pre-Roman Iron Age	MA	V. Rumyantsev	
102	Kaalepi	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Pewter medallion	End of 18th c	MA	E. Promm	E. Russow
103	Kaaruka	F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Coin, penannular brooch fragments, finger-rings, slag	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	E. Promm, A. Vares	M. Reppo
104	Kirisaare	F	Paide town (Peetri)	Gilt silver spur	13th c?	AI 8204	A. Vares	J. Kari
105	Kirisaare	H	Paide town (Peetri)	Fragments of silver jewellery (beads, finger-ring, sheet pendants, bracelet)	11th–12th c	AI 8154	A. Vares	Ü. Tamla
106	Lokuta	F	Türi	Finger-ring	Middle Ages	MA	R. Pahapill	
107	Lõõla	F	Türi	Bird-shaped pendant	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8209	E. Eeskivi	M. Reppo
108	Lõõla	F	Türi	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8208	E. Eeskivi	M. Reppo
109	Müüsleri	F	Järva (Peetri)	Push-key spring lock	12th–13th c	MA	O. Rubel	
110	Näsuvere	F	Türi	Pendant, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8241	R. Pahapill	H. Luik
111	Reopalu	F	Türi	Penannular brooch, rectangular ornament link	Late Iron Age	AI 8202	E. Eeskivi	M. Reppo
112	Rõa	C?, F	Türi	Pendants (horse-shaped, cruciform), mounts, ornament fragments, stoneware sherd	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8092	R. Lallu	M.-L. Posti

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113	Valasti	S, F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Coins, bells, trapezoid pendant, finger-rings, fragment of penannular brooch, burnt jewellery fragments, spearhead, mount, book clasp, punch, button	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	E. Promm, A. Vares	M. Reppo
114	Äiamaa	F	Türi	Cruciform pendant, finger-ring, buckle	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	R. Pahapill	
115	Ämbra	F	Järva (Peetri)	Pendant	Late Iron Age?	AI 8203	E. Eeskivi	M. Reppo
116	Öötla	F	Järva (Peetri)	Coin, coin pendant, belt fittings	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		A. Piirsalu	
117	Öötla	C?, F	Järva (Peetri)	Comb-shaped pendant, bell-shaped ornament link, mount, ring	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Piirsalu	
LÄÄNEMAA								
118	Erja	F	Haapsalu town (Ridala)	Gilt silver mount	14th c	MA	U. Pärna	E. Russow
119	Kuijõe	C?, S?	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Dress pin fragments, shield finger-ring, trapezoid pendant, belt fittings, rectangular ornament links, chain fragment, brooch needle, vessel lid	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	T. Toomsalu	
120	Liivi	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Mount, burnt copper alloy items	Late Iron Age?	MA	J. Ojabstein	
121	Liivi	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Coins, finger-ring, tripod fragment?, metal item	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	J. Ojabstein	
122	Niinja	C?	Lääne-Nigula (Martna)	Coins, pendants, finger-ring, chains, chain separator, belt fittings, copper alloy ingot	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8233	A. Pluss	H. Luik
LÄÄNE-VIRUMAA								
123	Andja	F	Rakvere (Haljala)	Round brooch	16th–17th c	MA	S. Zakharov	M. Reppo
124	Ebavere	C	Väike-Maarja	Crossbow-shaped brooch, burnt jewellery fragments (bracelets, dress pins, brooches, finger-rings, pendants, chain holders, chains, spiral tubes, rectangular ornament links), bells, beads, belt fittings, spearheads, axes, knives, horse harness parts, rivets	Late Iron Age	MA	A. Sats, L. Roots	
125	Jootme	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Fragment of cruciform pendant	12th–13th c	MA	A. Ksentsov	M. Reppo
126	Kestla	F	Viru-Nigula (Lüganuse)	Silver coins	10th–11th c	AI 8146	A. Krivtsov	M. Kiudsoo
127	Koila	F	Viru-Nigula	Fragment of enamelled brooch, penannular brooch, coins, button	Roman Iron Age, Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8205	A. Šovkunenko	M. Reppo
128	Nurmetu	F	Vinni (Väike-Maarja)	Axe-shaped pendant	12th–13th c	MA	K. Arukaev	T. Kurisoo

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129	Nõmmküla	F	Väike-Maarja (Ambla)	Coins, finger-rings, bell, ornament fragments, buttons	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	D. Doroškeviš	
130	Pada-Aruküla	F	Viru-Nigula	Crossbow-shaped brooch fragment, coin, penannular brooch, belt fittings, iron item	Pre-Viking Age – Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	K. Kartau	
131	Rägavere	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Coin pendant, finger-rings, bell, button, ring, pipe cleaning stick	Early Modern Period – Modern Period	MA	A. Ksentsov	
132	Räsna, Ambla	S, F	Tapa (Ambla)	Coins, bell, finger-ring fragment, belt fittings (mounts, buckles), button, rings, metal items	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	A. Ksentsov	
133	Räsna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Coin, bell, button, buckles, metal items	Early Modern Period, Modern Period	MA	A. Ksentsov	
134	Selja	C, F	Viru-Nigula (Haljala)	Jewellery fragments (dress pins, penannular brooches, pendants), bells, scale weight, mounts, knife head, nail, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8235	E. Geide	H. Luik
135	Vao	F	Väike-Maarja	Coin, penannular brooch	Late Iron Age	AI 8155	R. Ots	M. Kiudsoo
136	Venevere	S?, F	Vinni (Simuna)	Brooches (round small brooches), finger-rings, pendants (comb-shaped, coins), bells, tweezers, belt fittings, key fragment, bullets, buttons	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8098	S. Vinokurov	M.-L. Posti
PÕLVAMAA								
137	Jõepera	F	Räpina	Sieve-shaped pendant, finger-ring, coin, mounts, button, bullet, pewter objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA, TÕ 2853	I. Tsakuhhin, A. Kotkin	R. Juurik
138	Meerapalu, Pedaspää	F	Räpina (Võnnu, Räpina)	Coins, signet rings, finger-rings, small round brooches, heart-shaped brooch, coin pendants, rhomboid cruciform pendants, cruciform pendants, bells, jewellery fragments, buckle, mounts, buttons, knives, bullets, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	A. Kotkin, S. Kürsa, I. Tsakuhhin	
139	Meerapalu	F	Räpina (Võnnu)	Signet ring, finger-ring, cruciform pendant, buttons, ring	Early Modern Period – Modern Period	MA	A. Kotkin	
140	Meerapalu	S?, F	Räpina (Võnnu)	Coins, cruciform pendants, silver bead, ear spoon, belt fittings, buttons	Modern Period	TÕ 2804	I. Tsakuhhin	H. Luik
141	Mehikoorma	S?, F	Räpina	Coins, cruciform pendants	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA, TÕ 2811	S. Kürsa, I. Tsakuhhin	H. Luik

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PÄRNUMAA								
142	Eense	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Stone adze	Stone Age	MA	M. Annusvere	
143	Pärnu	F	Pärnu town (Pärnu)	Antler axe fragment	Middle Ages?	PäMu	M. Sildoja	M. Reppo
RAPLAMA								
144	Kohatu	F	Märjamaa	Mount, finger-ring	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	I. Letitski	
145	Kuusiku	F	Rapla	Penannular brooch, coin pendant, scale weight, jetton, buttons, ornament fragment	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	AI 8214	J. Truia	M. Reppo
146	Linnaaluste	S	Kehtna (Rapla)	Fragments of jewellery (bracelets, penannular brooches), belt fittings, knife head, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8148	T. Arukask	T. Kurisoo
147	Lümandu-Purga	C, S	Märjamaa	Coins, pendants, brooches, finger-rings, jewellery fragments, spiral tube, beads, sword scabbard chape, belt fittings, strike-a-light, buttons, rivets, book clasp, nails, rings, tobacco pipe fragment, seal, knife handle fragment, burnt metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA, AI 8236, AI 8158	T. Hiob, A. Skrõpnik	M. Reppo, T. Kurisoo, H. Luik
148	Sooniste	F	Märjamaa (Kullamaa)	Trapezoid pendant	Late Iron Age?	AI 8141	A. Haruk	K. Tasuja
SAAREMAA								
149	Hievälja	F	Saaremaa (Karja)	Animal-shaped pendant fragments, buckle	Late Iron Age; Middle Ages – Modern Period	AI 8095	R. Tähve	M.-L. Posti
150	Irased	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Finger-ring	Middle Ages	MA	T. Tohv	T. Kurisoo
151	Jööri	C, F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Scale weights, rectangular ornament links, jewellery fragments, buckles, nail, metal objects	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
152	Jõelega	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Brooch or buckle	Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	Ü. Tamla
153	Jõempa	F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Sword scabbard chape	Late Iron Age	MA	V. Poopuu	Ü. Tamla
154	Karida	F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Animal-shaped figurine, tobacco pipe cleaner	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	A. Kallas	
155	Karida	S?, F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Shield finger-ring, dress pin, spiral tubes, bracelet fragment, rectangular ornament links, round brooch, mounts, belt fittings, knife handle head, buttons, needle, nail	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	A. Kallas	
156	Kehila	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Pewter pendants	Middle Ages?	MA	Anonymous	

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157	Kehila	M	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Bracelet, cast iron ingots, knife fragments, iron tool fragments	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	E. Kessel	R. Saage
158	Kellamäe	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Scale weight	Viking Age	MA	K. Laane	M. Kiudsoo
159	Kotsma, Lümanda-Kulli	C, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Small round brooches, heart-shaped brooch, brooch needles, metal bead, bell, mounts, buckle, ornament link, ornament fragment, tweezers, needles, knife, knife handle fragment	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
160	Kurevere	C, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Burnt jewellery fragments (penannular brooch), belt fittings (mounts, buckle), rectangular ornament link, metal objects	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
161	Kõrkküla	H?, F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Coins	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
162	Kõruse	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Finger-rings	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
163	Lassi	F	Saaremaa (Anseküla)	Signet ring fragment, mounts, seal?	Early Modern Period – Modern Period	MA	A. Raun	
164	Lassi	F	Saaremaa (Anseküla)	Coin, pewter pendant	Middle Ages	MA	A. Raun	
165	Leedri	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coin, bracteate, finger-ring	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	K. Laane, T. Tohv	M. Kiudsoo, T. Kurisoo
166	Leedri	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coin, brooch needle	Late Iron Age?	MA	T. Tohv	T. Kurisoo
167	Leedri	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Trapezoid pendants	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	T. Tohv	
168	Linnaka	F	Saaremaa (Karja)	Dress pin fragment, seal	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	R. Pärn	
169	Linnuse	F	Muhu	Scale weights, rectangular ornament link	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	
170	Loona	C?	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Knife sheath, bracelet, scale weight	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	M. Tammert
171	Läägi	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, finger-ring, pendant, small round brooch, heart-shaped brooch, beads, strap end, tweezers	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
172	Lööne	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	Ü. Tamla
173	Lümanda	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Rectangular ornament links	12th–13th c	MA	K. Laane, T. Tohv	T. Kurisoo
174	Lümanda	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Animal-head-shaped brooch	Viking Age	MA	K. Laane	
175	Lümanda-Kulli	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Mount	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	
176	Maleva	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Dress pin fragment, penannular brooch fragment	Late Iron Age	MA	E. Kessel	

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177	Meedla	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Bronze socketed axe, iron socketed axe, knife fragments	Bronze Age – Migration Period	MA	E. Kessel	
178	Mullutu	HS	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Dress pins, chain holders, chains, brooches, bracelets, finger-rings, pendants, bells, belt fittings, animal figurine, scale weights, scabbard chapes, pommel, arrowheads, bolt, knives, axes, spur, harness parts, sickle, rivets, nails, hobnails, metal items	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	SM 10863	T. Tohv, K. Laane	M. Mägi
179	Pähkla	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Coins, metal bead, pendants, belt fittings (mounts, buckles, strap end), finger-rings, rectangular ornament links, thimbles, needle, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	A. Kallas	
180	Rahu	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Rectangular ornament link	Late Iron Age	MA	R. Pärn	
181	Saaremetsa	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Chain separator, coin pendants	Late Iron Age, Early Modern Period	MA	S. Kesküla	
182	Tammese	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, cruciform pendant, mounts, button, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	E. Kessel	
183	Vahva	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Penannular brooch	12th–13th c	MA	K. Laane, T. Tohv	
184	Vaivere	F	Saaremaa (Püha)	Coins, ornament fragment, slag	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	MA	P. E. Mustonen	G.-K. Lutter
185	Vanalõve	C?	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Spearheads, seaxes	Middle Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	T. Kurisoo
186	Varpe	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Chain holder, scale weight, knife sheath chape	Late Iron Age	MA	T. Tohv, K. Laane	T. Kurisoo
187	Varpe	C, S, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, jewellery fragments (dress pins, pendants, brooches), finger-rings, penannular brooches, bells, pewter plaque, buttons, metal items	Middle Iron Age, Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	T. Tohv, K. Laane, T. Vares	T. Kurisoo, M. Kiudsoo, I. Leimus
188	Varpe	H	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins	Viking Age	MA	K. Laane	I. Leimus, M. Kiudsoo
189	Vedruka	C, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, sword pommel?, mounts, finger-rings, small round brooch, buckles, metal objects, tobacco pipe cover	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
190	Veere	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Chain holders with chain	Late Iron Age	MA	A. Kula	
191	Viidu-Mäebe	SP	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Dress pin	Pre-Viking Age	MA	Anonymous	
192	Väike-Ula	F	Saaremaa (Jämaja)	Iron axe	Late Iron Age?	MA	A. Talk	

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TARTUMAA							
193 Ahunapalu (Ahunapalu Leego)	S	Kastre (Võnnu)	Finger-rings, comb-shaped pendant fragments	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	TÜ 2852, TÜ 2856	A. Kotkin, I. Tsakuhhin	R. Juurik
194 Ahunapalu (Ahunapalu Mäha)	S	Kastre (Võnnu)	Cruciform pendant, brooch fragments, bracelet frag- ment, signet ring, bell, coin	Late Iron Age – Early Modern Period	TÜ 2805	I. Tsakuhhin	H. Luik
195 Kardla	F	Tartu town (Tartu-Maarja)	Rectangular ornament link	12th–13th c	MA	D. Šutov	
196 Kasepää	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Sword scabbard chape, penannular brooch	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages	TÜ 2850, TÜ 2854	I. Tsakuhhin, A. Kotkin	R. Juurik
197 Kauda	F	Peipsiääre (Maarja- Magdaleena)	Knife sheath chape	Modern Period	TÜ 2812	I. Tsakuhhin	H. Luik
198 Koruste	F	Elva (Rõngu)	Coin, penannular brooch, signet ring, mount, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
199 Kõduküla	C	Elva (Rõngu)	Coin pendant, bracelet fragment, iron object	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
200 Lapetukme	C, F	Elva (Rannu)	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, dress pins, penannular brooches, finger-rings, bell, cruciform pendant), strike-a-light	7th–8th c, Late Iron Age, Middle Ages	TÜ 2916	Anonymous	H. Luik
201 Paluküla	F	Kastre (Võnnu)	Bracelet fragment	Late Iron Age	MA	T. Sei	
202 Pedaste	F	Elva (Rõngu)	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (pendants, brace- lets, chains), metal objects	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	TÜ 2918	Anonymous	H. Luik
203 Piiri	F	Tartu (Võnnu)	Coins, cruciform pendant, star-shaped brooch, signet rings, buttons, net weight	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA, TÜ 2808	I. Tsakuhhin, S. Kürsa, A. Kotkin	H. Luik
204 Praaga	S	Peipsiääre (Võnnu)	Coins, finger-rings, cruci- form pendants, brooches, bells, spearhead, axe, key, belt fittings, mounts, buttons, knives, knife handle fragments, horse shoes, bullets, rings, nails, iron tools, shoe fragments, metal blooms and ingots, parts of fishing equipment, tobacco pipe cleaner	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	I. Tsakuhhin, A. Kotkin, S. Kürsa	R. Saage, A. Tvauri
205 Purtsi	F	Elva (Rõngu)	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, fin- ger-rings, bells), brooches, cruciform pendant, metal belt fittings, scale weight, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2917	Anonymous	H. Luik
206 Põvvatu	C?, F	Luunja (Tartu-Maarja)	Small round brooches, heart-shaped brooches, finger-ring, penannular brooch fragment, belt fittings, burnt metal items, nails, buttons, bullets, metal items	Late Iron Age? – Modern Period	MA	A. Kasemets	

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207	Raigaste	S	Elva (Rõngu)	Coins, finger-rings (signet rings), small round brooches, bracelet, metal beads, fragments of copper alloy jewellery, mounts, belt fittings, locks, keys, buttons, pewter vessel fragments, bullets, cannon ball, fragments of metal items	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
208	Raigaste	H	Elva (Rõngu)	Pewter jug fragments, large silver beads, beads (amber, chalcedony, pewter, glass)	Late Medieval – Early Modern Period	TÜ 2889	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
209	Rannaküla	S	Elva (Rannu)	Coins, bell, finger-rings, mount, jewellery fragments (bracelets, brooch needle), button, thimble	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
210	Rannaküla	C	Elva (Rannu)	Coins, round brooch, bell, buckle, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	
211	Rebaste	C?, F?	Elva (Rõngu)	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (dress pin, brooches, bracelets, finger-ring), small round brooch, metal bead, coin pendant, metal objects	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2920	Anonymous	H. Luik
212	Saare	F	Tartu (Võnnu)	Coins, penannular brooch, signet rings, finger-rings, buttons, spindle whorl?, ornament fragments, rings, metal objects	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA, TÜ 2851, 2857	A. Kotkin, S. Kõirsa, I. Tsakuhhin	R. Juurik
213	Selgise	F	Peipsiääre (Maarja-Magdaleena)	Iron axe	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	T. Kurisoo
214	Tedreküla	C, F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Coins, brooch fragments, rectangular ornament link, bells, belt fittings	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ	J. Festsenko	M.-L. Posti
215	Tilga	S	Elva (Rõngu)	Signet rings, finger rings, counting jetton, small round brooch, iron penannular brooch, buckle, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2888	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
216	Tooni	F	Tartu (Võnnu)	Coins, cruciform pendants, finger-rings, brooches, ear-ring, ear spoon, belt fittings, buttons, metal ornaments and items	Viking Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2807	I. Tsakuhhin	H. Luik
217	Uhti	F	Kambja (Tartu-Maarja)	Iron axe	Late Iron Age	TÜ 2773	P. Prams	Ü. Tamla
218	Varnja	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Coins, pendants, finger-rings, bracelet, brooches, buttons, bell	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2810, 2848, 2849, 2855	I. Tsakuhhin, A. Kotkin	H. Luik, R. Juurik
219	Varnja	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Sword scabbard chape, penannular brooch	Late Iron Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2894	D. Doroškevitš	M. Reppo, H. Luik
220	Vehendi	F	Elva (Rannu)	Penannular brooch, small round brooch	Modern Period	TÜ 2893	E. Jegorov	R. Juurik
221	Voika	F	Nõo	Coin fragment, signet ring	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	MA	E. Jegorov	

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VALGAMAA								
222	Killinge	H, S	Valga (Sangaste)	Ornament of coins and chains, signet rings, thimble, brooch fragment, wheel-thrown pottery	Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2843	Anonymous	R. Rammo
223	Kiviküla	S	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, copper alloy and pewter jewellery, belt fittings, 2 mounts, thimbles, metal objects	Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2841, 2923	Anonymous	M. Tammet, R. Rammo
224	Otepää	S, C	Otepää	Coins, silver sheet pendant, pendants, finger ring, bells, bracelets, spiral tubes, grinding stone, rings, belt fittings, scale weights, thimble, pottery, burnt metal objects (jewellery), slag, nails, fork	Viking Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2895, 2896	M. Kivistik	M. Reppo
225	Prange	S, C?	Otepää (Sangaste)	Fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, penannular brooches, chain, mount), bells, signet ring, small round brooches, coin pendants, scale weight, iron strike-a-light	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 2919	Anonymous	H. Luik
226	Soontaga	H	Tõrva (Rõngu)	Round and rectangular sheet pendants, spiral tubes	16th–17th c	TÜ 2748	A. Berjzokin	A. Tvauri
227	Uniküla	S	Valga (Sangaste)	Small round pendant, steelyard counterweight	Middle Ages – Modern Period	MA	Anonymous	M. Tammet
228	Õruste	C	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, brooches, finger-ring, needle case, belt fittings, knife sheath fragment, metal objects	Middle Ages – Modern Period	TÜ 2922	Anonymous	M. Tammet
VILJANDIMAA								
229	Kobruvere	F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Penannular brooches, star-shaped brooch, bells, finger-ring fragment, needle-case, buttons, metal objects	Middle Ages- Modern Period	TÜ 2784	Search team of St Matthew's Day Battlefield	
230	Kobruvere	S, F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Coins, penannular brooch fragments, rectangular ornament links, finger-rings, bracelet fragments, pendants, bells, burnt metal items, belt fittings, buttons, metal objects, pottery	Late Iron Age- Modern Period	TÜ 2785	Search team of St Matthew's Day Battlefield	
231	Kookla	F	Viljandi	Chain holder, ornament fragments	Late Iron Age, Modern Period	MA	R. Ots	T. Kurisoo
232	Maalasti	C, S?	Põhja-Sakala (Pilistvere)	Coin, burnt metal objects, rectangular ornament link, bracelet, heart-shaped brooch, ring, pipe cleaner, spur, stirrup, pottery, flint	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	G. Kallas	
233	Pinska	F	Viljandi	Seal with coat of arms	18th c?	MA	S. Šovkunenko	M. Reppo
234	Sürgavere	H	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Coins	10th–11th c	MA	R. Ots	I. Leimus

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235 Sürgavere	F, C?	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Bronze axe fragment, bracelet, cruciform pendant, finger-rings, brooch needle, heart- shaped brooch, rectangular ornament link, belt fittings, buttons, spur fragment, bullets	Bronze Age, Late Iron Age – Modern Period	MA	R. Ots	T. Kurisoo

VÕRUMAA

236 Pindi	C	Võru (Rõuge)	Sword scabbard chape	Late Iron Age	MA	Anonymous	
237 Uue-Antsla	F	Antsla (Urvaste)	Bracelet fragment, mount fragment	12th–13th c, Modern Period	TÜ 2892	J. Kiidron	R. Juurik

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2019. AASTA DETEKTORI- JA JUHULEIUD NING UUS MUINSUSKAITSESEADUS

Tuuli Kurisoo, Riina Rammo ja Maria Smirnova

Artikkel annab ülevaate otsinguvahendi abil ja juhulikult avastatud arheoloogilistest leidudest, mis jõudsid 2019. aasta jooksul Muinsuskaitseametisse. Artikli lõpus võetakse kokku hobitsimisega seotud muudatused uues Muinsuskaitseseaduses ja hinnatakse, kuidas on selle rakendamine praktikas kujunenud. Uus seadus on tõenäoliselt ka üks põhjusi, miks 2019. aastal on MA-le antud üle tunduvalt rohkem esemeid kui eelnevalt. Ülevaate aluseks on tabelis 1 esitatud informatsioon leiupaikade ja esemete kohta (jn 1). Leidude ajaline ja ruumiline jaotus kattub suures osas eelnevate aastatega. Kindlate muististega on arvukaid leiukohti võimalik siduda siiski harva ja seega on suurem osa avastustest määratletud juhuleidudena. Tabelist on välja jäetud esemed, mida pole õnnestunud liigiliselt või ajaliselt määrata. Niisamuti ei kajastu tabelis mõned üksikesemed ja vaid 19.–20. sajandi dateeringuga leiukogumid (nt nõöbid, piibuorgid, mündid).

Kõige arvukamalt on tabelis leiukohti põhjapoolsest Eestist – Harjumaalt, Ida- ja Lääne-Virumaalt, Raplamaalt ja Järvamaalt. Mitmed paigad on olnud detektoristide otsimiskohtadeks juba aastaid (nt nr 55, 78–81, 84, 99, 104, 105, 116, 117, 146, 147). Kõige vanemad leiud on pronksiaegsed putkkirved Puhkovast (jn 2) ja Soldinast (nr 74). Pronksiaega või rauaaja algusesse võib kuuluda ka Kantkülast (nr 9) pärit jahvekiivi. Varasest rauaajast on teavet erandliku eelrooma rauaagekse kirve (nr 101), rooma rauaagesete ehete (nr 1, 11, 58, 67, 127) ja rooma mündi (nr 32) kohta. Suhteliselt arvukalt toodi MA-sse 2019. aastal rooma rauaajal või keskmise rauaaja alguses valmistatud rauast putkkirveid (nr 62, 72, 73, 83, 85). Keskmisest rauaajast on teada vaid üksikud ehted ja nende katked (nr 12, 61, 130).

Paljud leiukogumid on dateeritud laia perioodi nooremast rauaajast uusajani. Viikingiaegsed esemed on enamasti mündid ja ehted, millest kõige tähelepanuväärsemad on Varjast leitud Ojamaa päritolu karpsõlg (jn 3) ja suur ammukujuline sõlg Ebaverest (nr 124). Ehted ja rõivastusega seotud esemed on ülekaalus ka hilisrauaagesete leidude hulgas. Erilistena leidudena saab välja tuua liivlastele omase taimornamendiga keekandja (nr 7) ja Eestis haruldast tüüpi kirvekujulise ripatsi (nr 128). Arvukad kesk- ja uusaegsed leiud on pigem iseloomulikud maa-asulatele või ka -kalmistutele (nt sõled, sõrmused, kuljused, ripatsid, naastud, nõöbid, mündid).

Palju vähem on teavet läänepoolsest Eestist, kus teadaolevalt tehti avastusi tänapäevasel Läänemaal, Pärnumaal ja Saaremaal. Vaid viis paika on teada Läänemaal (nr 118–122) ja kaks Pärnumaalt (nr 142, 143). Positiivse arenguna saab esile tõsta Saaremaad, kust üle antud esemete arv on märkimisväärselt kasvanud. Lisaks arvukatele juhuleidudele leiti seal eriaegseid kalmeid (nr 151, 159, 160, 187, 189), viikingiaegne aare (nr 188) ja asulakoht (nr 187). Üks ehtenõel on seotud tänaseks kaitse all oleva Viidumäe ohverdämiskohaga (nr 191). Kindlasti väärib esiletõstmist leidude põhjal eelviikingiaegst alates ja veel keskajal kasutusel olnud Mullutu sadamakoht (nr 178).

Sarnaselt teistele Eesti piirkondadele on ka Lääne-Eestist ja saartelt leide arvukamalt alles alates nooremast rauaajast, varasemate perioodide esemeid tuleb ette vähem (nr 142, 177, 185). Kui enamik nooremassa raua- ja ajaloolise aja leidudest esindavad piirkonnas levinud tüüpe, siis Eesti kontekstis on unikaalne Skandinaavia päritolu viikingiaegne loomapeakujuline sõlg (nr 174) ja lisaks eelpool mainitud Varja

leiule veel ühe väljaspool Gotlandi haruldase karp-sõle jäänused Mullutust (nr 178). Märkimisväärne on ka kuldamisjälgedega Ringerike stiilis 11. sajandi mõõganupp, mis tabelis küll ei kajastu, sest selle täpne leiukoht on teadmata. Arvukad kesk- ja uusaegsed juhuleidudena märgitud ehted ja rõivastuse osad viitavad ilmselt kunagistele elukohtadele ja vahel ka matmispaikadele. Erandlik on juhuslikult Pärnu rannast leitud sarvest keskaegne kirves (jn 4), sest analoogseid esemeid on Eestist teada alla kümne. Kehilast avastatud malmkangid (nr 157) võivad osutada seal paiknenud uusaegsele sepikojale.

Võrreldes põhjapoolse Eestiga on vähem teada ka Lõuna-Eesti kohta: tabelis on seitse kirjet Viljandi- maalt, viis Põlvamaalt, seitse Valgamaalt ja kaks Võrumaalt. Rohkem on teavet Jõgevamaa (13 kirjet) ja Tartumaa (29 kirjet) kohta. Viimasel juhul võib tõus olla osalt tingitud kasvavast huvist Peipsi-äärsete piirkondade vastu, kusjuures arvukalt kogutakse leide kaldalähedasest madalast veest (nr 137–139, 141, 196, 203, 204, 212, 216, 218). Ehkki need kogumid sisaldavad leide alates viikingiajast (nr 216) ja hilisrauaajast (nt jn 6), on ülekaalus siiski keskaja lõpu ja uusaja juhuleidudena käsitletavat esemed (nt mündid, pitsatsõrmused, kaelaristid, nõöbid, kuulid). Osasid Praagalt kogutud leidudest (nr 204) saab siiski tõe-

näoliselt seostada 16.–17. sajandi vahipostiga, mis asus Emajõe kunagises suubumiskohas olnud saarel.

Lõunapoolsetest maakondadest 2019. aastal üle antud avastusi saab suhteliselt sageli seostada pika-aegsete asulakohtadega (nr 94, 98, 193, 194, 204, 207, 209, 215, 222–225, 227, 230) või ka eriaegsete ja -tüübiliste matmispaikadega (nt nr 93, 94, 199, 200, 210, 214, 228, 232). Käsitletavast piirkonnast on teada neli aaret, millest üks kuulub viikingiaega (nr 234) ja ülejäänud kolm sisaldavad peamiselt 16. sajandi lõpule ja 17. sajandi algusele iseloomulikke münte ja ehteid (nr 208, 222, 226; jn 5).

Alates 2011. aastast kehtinud Muinsuskaitseaduse järgi pidid hobiotsijad loa saamiseks läbima koolituse vaid siis, kui eesmärgiks oli leida kultuuriväärtusega esemeid. Uus Muinsuskaitseadus, mis jõustus 1. mail 2019, reguleerib otsinguvahendi kasutamist senisest täpsemalt. Nüüd on otsinguvahendi (metallidetektor, sonar, magnet) luba vaja alati väljaspool tiheasustust. Lisaks on hobiotsijatel kohustus teavitada MA-d enne otsingule minekut ja iga käigu kohta tuleb ühe kuu jooksul esitada aruanne. Sel-line kord võiks anda parema võimaluse ebaseaduslike tegevuste tõkestamiseks. Loodetavasti kiireneb ka hobiotsijatele antav tagasiside ning leiud jõuavad kiiremini konservaatorite ja uurijateni.